

INTRODUCTION TO THE INTERVIEW ¹

This study was conducted as part of a master's thesis in Environmental Engineering at the Instituto Superior Técnico. Its objective was to investigate the resilience of fishing activity in the Luiz Saldanha Marine Park (LSMP). This research employs an approach that combines surveys and interviews with the objective of advancing academic understanding, furnishing insights that can inform a more participatory decision-making process, and contributing to a more inclusive and equitable planning of the marine park. By examining the interaction between the fishing community and the marine environment, we aim to comprehend the challenges confronting fishermen and to identify avenues for enhancing their capacity to adapt to diverse challenges and promote sustainable resource management practices in the LSMP.

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TEMPLATE OF INTERVIEW OF THE IPMA, I.P. REPRESENTATIVE

1. Can you briefly share your background and experience in the field of marine biology, and how it led you to be involved in the Luiz Saldanha Marine Park?
2. In your role within the marine biology field, how closely have you interacted with the SSF community in the Luiz Saldanha Marine Park?
3. What are the main species for SSF? How would you rate the evolution of key species for the SSF through time in the LSMP? And ecologically important species? How would you classify the ecological evolution of the park until today?
4. Do you consider that the scientific community have relationships with the fishers? Regarding social relationships within the community, including cooperation and collaboration with the fishers, how would you assess the strength and depth of these interactions? Do you collaborate with them in monitoring activities? Do you think there are advantages to strengthening these connections? How would you do that?
5. In your experience, how adaptable were the SSF community to changing environmental conditions, particularly in adjusting fishing practices?
6. How would you define the resilience of small-scale fisheries in both social and ecological terms? How might this definition align or differ from the perceptions of local fishermen?

¹ O texto introdutório sofria pequenas alterações de modo a estar adequado ao perfil do entrevistado.

TEMPLATE OF INTERVIEW OF THE ICNF REPRESENTATIVE

1. Please provide a concise overview of your experience in managing marine protected areas (MPAs) and your current role within the institution.
2. Please outline the principal objectives and future goals of ICNF in the management of the Luiz Saldanha Marine Park.
3. What are the principal challenges currently facing the ICNF in the management of the PMLS and the conservation of marine resources?
4. To what extent is your role concerned with interactions with the fishing community in the Luiz Saldanha Marine Park?
5. Please describe the socio-economic characteristics of the artisanal fishermen in Sesimbra. In your opinion, how have these communities evolved, and what impact has the marine protected area had on them?
6. What is the ICNF's perspective on the role of local fishermen in marine conservation and park management?
7. Please describe the social relations within the fishing community, and also those between the fishermen and other users of the marine park. To what extent does POPNA influence these relationships? To what extent does the POPNA consider the well-being and resilience of fishermen? To what extent can this be said to be the case?
8. Does the POPNA facilitate collective action by fishermen in defining the governance and management of the park? What mechanisms, if any, could be put in place to promote this dynamic?
9. In your experience, how crucial is it to incorporate local knowledge into decision-making processes?
10. Please outline the main objectives and future goals of the ICNF in relation to the management of the Luiz Saldanha Marine Park.
11. Please define the term 'resilience' as it applies to small-scale fisheries.
12. Please provide your opinion on the potential value of convening a session to discuss the results of the study with all relevant stakeholders. If you are in favour of this course of action, please indicate the format or type of session that you believe would be most conducive to a constructive debate.

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TEMPLATE OF INTERVIEW OF THE DGRM REPRESENTATIVE

1. Please provide a concise overview of your experience in the management of small-scale fisheries in Portugal, as well as your current role within the institution.

2. Please outline the principal objectives and goals of the DGRM with regard to small-scale fisheries, both in the immediate future and in the longer term.
3. Please describe the impact of varying levels of regulation and legislation on small-scale fisheries. This is to say, at the European and national levels.
4. To what extent is your role characterised by interactions with the fishing community in the Luiz Saldanha Marine Park?
5. Please describe the socio-economic characteristics of the artisanal fishermen in Sesimbra. In your view, how have these communities evolved, and what impact has the marine protected area had on them?
6. Please describe the nature of the DGRM's relationship with the artisanal fishermen of the PMLS. Furthermore, what is the relationship between the ICNF and the aforementioned parties?
7. Please confirm whether you are aware of the process of revising the POPNA and converting it into a programme. What has been the role of the DGRM in this process?
8. Please describe your knowledge of previous experiences of participatory processes in the management of the PMLS. Please provide an assessment of these processes and indicate what future they may have.
9. Please define the term 'resilience' as it applies to small-scale fisheries.
10. Please provide your opinion on the potential value of convening a session to discuss the results of the study with all stakeholders. Should a constructive debate be held, what format or type of session would be most effective in facilitating it?

TEMPLATE OF INTERVIEW OF THE CMS REPRESENTATIVE

1. Please describe your current role at CM Sesimbra. At what point in time did you become involved with the PMLS? Please provide a concise overview of your experience with the Marine Park and the local fishing community.
2. Over the course of time, how would you characterise the relationship between the executive and the management organisation? To what extent has the municipality contributed to the park's management strategy, and to what extent has the park influenced the municipality's strategy?
3. Please describe the socio-economic characteristics of the artisanal fishermen in Sesimbra at the present time. In your view, how have these characteristics evolved over time, and what impact has the MPA had on them?
4. Please describe the social relations within the fishing community based on your experience. To what extent is the fishing industry and the Park perceived as beneficial to the wider population of Sesimbra?

5. To what extent do you believe that the fishing community is capable of contributing to the municipal strategy regarding the park and fishing? To what extent might the council facilitate greater involvement by fishermen in the management of the PMLS?
6. Has the council been made aware of any instances of conflict between fishermen and other park users? Please provide your thoughts on past experiences, such as MARGov. Please provide your assessment. What potential does this approach have for future development?
7. In considering the future of artisanal fishing in the Luiz Saldanha Marine Park, what prospective scenarios do you envisage? Please indicate whether there are any particular initiatives or changes that you believe would be beneficial to the fishing community and enhance its resilience.
8. Please define the term 'resilience' as it applies to small-scale fishing.
9. What is your opinion on the convening of a session for the discussion of the study's findings with all relevant stakeholders? If you are in favour of this course of action, please indicate the format or type of session that you believe would be most conducive to a constructive debate.

TEMPLATE OF INTERVIEW OF THE AAPCS REPRESENTATIVE

1. Please elucidate the historical development, mission statement and objectives of the Association of Artisanal and Local Fishermen of the Centre and South. Please describe the principal responsibilities and activities of your role as representatives of the SSF in the marine park.
2. Please describe the methods employed to engage with stakeholders in the small-scale fisheries (SSF) sector and to ensure that their voices are heard in decision-making processes related to the management of the marine park. To what extent is there a willingness within the community to participate and unite around common goals?
3. To what extent has the community undergone change since the implementation of the park? Please describe the socio-economic characteristics of the artisanal fishermen in Sesimbra.
4. To what extent do you believe the community is capable of influencing the implementation of management strategies by the PMLS that directly affect the practice of fishing? What is the optimal approach for the management body to adopt in order to facilitate this empowerment?
5. Please describe the methods by which collaboration with park authorities or other stakeholders is undertaken to address issues or concerns related to social protection within the scope of the POPNA.

6. It would be beneficial to ascertain whether there are any cultural norms, that is to say, any traditions or influences from older generations, that condition the way fishing is practised in the PMLS. If so, which ones?
7. Please describe the ways in which the community participates in knowledge-sharing networks and the extent to which local knowledge is taken into account when decisions are made. Do you believe that spatial planning documents that consider this factor can enhance the well-being and resilience of local fishermen?
8. In your opinion, what has been the impact of the POPNA on the communities and activities of fishermen in the PMLS? Have there been any positive or negative consequences of implementing the POPNA for local fishermen, and if so, what are they?
9. Please describe the principal challenges or concerns that SSF face as a consequence of POPNA regulations or management measures. Are there any particular provisions or aspects of POPNA that SSF consider particularly problematic or restrictive?
10. Please describe the resilience of small-scale fisheries in social and ecological terms. To what extent does this definition correspond with or diverge from the perceptions of local fishermen?
11. In considering the future of artisanal fishing in the Luiz Saldanha Marine Park, what prospective scenarios emerge? Please indicate whether there are any particular initiatives or changes that you believe would be beneficial to the fishing community and enhance its resilience.
12. What is your opinion on the convening of a session for the discussion of the results of the study with all the stakeholders involved? If you are in favour of this course of action, please indicate the format or type of session that you believe would be most conducive to a constructive debate.